

Utilization of Open Video Repository-Assisted Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) on Computer Network Basics Course : Its Effect on Student Interest and Learning Outcomes

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Abstract:

Learning models that are not suitable in learning can make students' interests and learning outcomes less than optimal. Therefore, educators must make the selection of the right learning model. This study aims to investigate how Inquiry-Based Learning supported by an open video repository impacts student interest and learning outcomes. The research design used was a pseudo-experimental method with a pretest posttest control group design. The class that was given the treatment of using the Inquiry Based Learning learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository was an experimental class, while the control class used the Discovery Learning learning model. The population and samples used were class TJKT 1 as an experimental class and class TJKT 2 as a control class. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire instrument and the value of student learning outcomes which is then tested using SPSS. After conducting data analysis, data were obtained (1) sig(2-tailed) values of $0.047 < 0.05$ (2) sig(2-tailed) values of $0.000 < 0.05$ (3) student learning interest gain tests in experimental classes 0.32 greater than control classes 0.16 (4) gain tests of student learning outcomes in experimental classes 0.68 were greater than control classes 0.44. It can be concluded that in the use of the Inquiry Based Learning learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository there is a significant influence and has increased effectiveness compared to those who do not use the model on student interest and learning outcomes in the subject basics of Computer Network Engineering and Telecommunications.

Keywords: *Interest in Learning, Inquiry Based Learning (IBL), Learning Outcomes, Open Video Repository.*

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Introduction

Learning success is influenced by learners' interests and learning outcomes (Hermawan et al., 2022). Students can be said to have a high interest in learning if in the learning process they have a feeling of pleasure, concentrate attention, are involved in every learning process, and have an interest in learning (Mutlifah & Kaltsum, 2022). Interest in learning is an effort to learn something with a feeling of pleasure, so students will find it easier to get knowledge (Astuti, 2015). Interest in learning is a factor that has a dominant influence on student learning outcomes. Learning outcomes are an ability obtained by students after participating in learning activities, factors that can affect student learning outcomes include internal and external factors. Internal factors are psychological factors derived from the student's interest in learning, motivation, as well as readiness. External factors come from the environment and facilities and infrastructure during the teaching and learning process (Nurhasanah & Sobandi, 2016).

In the learning process, there is a learning model which is a whole series of presentations of teaching materials to achieve effective learning objectives. With technological advancements in the field of education, numerous new and more effective learning models have been introduced for use in educational activities. One of them is the Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model. The Inquiry Based Learning learning model is a student-centered learning model where students are given the opportunity to perform analysis and apply what has been learned to problems similar to those encountered in the real world (Kor et al., 2022). Inquiry model is a learning model that emphasizes the process of critical and analytical thinking to find and find answers to a question asked (Janah & Subroto, 2019).

When making observations at one of the vocational schools, the learning model used is Discovery Learning, during the use of this learning model there is a problem of lack of student interest when learning activities and student learning outcomes are low, characterized by students' lack of understanding of the material that has been given, students are less active during the learning process, and the number of students whose scores have not reached the minimum completion criteria (KKM).

Based on these problems, there is potential that can be developed to add and hone skills in overcoming problems faced by schools, namely by changing the learning model that has been used previously into an Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository. The Open Video Repository contains learning materials and videos uploaded on the website so that it can be used to help students understand the learning materials and make it easier for students to study alone at home. Learning media is essential in teaching and learning endeavors as it significantly contributes to supporting student learning outcomes and fostering enthusiasm for learning. Moreover, it serves as a valuable tool for educators, aiding them in effectively conveying messages to students (Hibra et al., 2019). Media encompasses all forms that can provoke the thoughts, emotions, attention, and interests of students in a manner conducive to acquiring knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Learning media types include print, audio-visual, graphic, and static projection.(Mudasih & Subroto, 2019).

Media that are often used for learning are powerpoint media, videos, and so on. PowerPoint media aids teachers in delivering subject matter by offering features such as the inclusion of graphics, images, text, photos, and sounds, as well as the ability to insert word art and establish transition effects for seamless movement between slides. Video media serves as a human intermediary tool for conveying messages, ideas, opinions, and concepts through the integration of images and sounds, thereby engaging the senses of sight and hearing to enhance the interest of the intended audience. The learning rate of students who use video media has increased compared to those who use powerpoint media (Mudasih & Subroto, 2019). Along with the development of technology, there is a platform that can be used to help educators in publishing videos, namely Youtube. Youtube is a platform that is very easily accessible through smartphones, laptops, and computers. However, there are still shortcomings in the use of Youtube, namely many videos that are not related to the subject matter (Mahendra, 2020). Therefore, researchers choose to create an open video repository website so that students are more focused on learning, because on Youtube it is likely that students will be more interested in watching other videos. In addition to youtube there is a google classroom platform that teachers can use as a provider of learning materials that students can access (Unitomo, 2022). However, only students who have joined the class can access the material. Unlike google classroom or other learning media, the advantage of using this open video repository website is that it can be accessed without the help of applications that overload the smartphone memory, just use the built-in browser from the smartphone. A website is a system on the internet as an information provider that allows anyone to access it (Nugroho, 2012).

The selection of the Open Video Repository as a medium in this learning is to make it easier for students to find learning references and assist in the implementation of practicum, especially in computer assembly materials, because with the implementation of an independent curriculum where students are freed to look for learning resources and many students use the internet in looking for learning resources so that this is one of the reasons in making this open video repository website. The Open Video Repository is an online repository used to collect, retrieve, and share videos to the public over the internet (Yassine et al., 2020).

The Open Video Repository is applied at the conceptualization stage, where students are given an understanding of the concept of the problem to produce a hypothesis that can then be researched. The Inquiry Based Learning learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository will be applied in the subject basics of Computer Network and Telecommunication Engineering on the element "Basic Orientation of Computer Network and Telecommunication Engineering".

This study aims to determine differences and improvements in the use of inquiry-based learning models assisted by open video repositories on the interests and learning outcomes of students.

Research Method

The research design employed in this study was a quasi-experimental method. The quasi-experimental method is a method carried out in two classes with the same material but given different treatment (Sunami, M. & Aslam, 2021). This quasi-experimental research is used to test the hypothesis of the influence of actions with other actions by controlling variables according to existing conditions. Variable control is performed on only one variable, which is considered the most important variable (Elpira & Ghufroon, 2015). In this study, a quasi-experimental design utilizing a pretest-posttest control group design was employed.

Population is the entire object of study for which the data will be taken (Nurrahmah et al., 2021). The population in this study were students of SMK N 1 Sawit, Boyolali. The samples used in this study were class X TJKT 1 and X TJKT 2, with the number of students in each class being 36 students. In this study, the sampling technique used was the stratified random sampling method. Stratified random sampling is a sampling technique that takes into account a level (stratification) in a population of elements grouped by character.

The data collection technique used is a pseudo-experimental design in pretest-posttest control group design. The pseudo-experimental design is carried out with one treatment, the data collection technique carried out is by being given a pretest and posttest which are used for learning outcomes tests and providing questionnaires / questionnaires to find out students' learning interests. A good test instrument must meet the test requirements, namely validity and reliability tests.

Validity test is the accuracy of a test instrument used as a measuring tool for learning outcomes (Amalia & Widayati, 2012). An instrument can be called valid if it actually measures what it should be measuring. The formula used to calculate the validity test is to use the Product Moment formula.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

To determine the validity result of the value of r, a decision is taken on the basis of the calculated price of rxy or rcount is consulted at the calculated price r with a significant degree of 5%. The reliability test is used to measure the reliability of the instrument using the formula to calculate the value of the Alpha coefficient.

$$\alpha = \left[\frac{k}{k-1} \right] \left[1 - \frac{\sum S_i^2}{S_t^2} \right]$$

In the learning outcomes instrument, tests of the level of difficulty, differentiating power, and distractor are carried out. The difficulty level test is shown by the question item, if the question item is not too difficult and not too easy, the difficulty level in the question item of learning outcomes can be said to be good [16]. In other words, the difficulty level of the test is moderate or sufficient. The difficulty level of each item is calculated by the formula:

$$TK = \frac{Jn}{Js}$$

The criteria for explaining the level of difficulty can be seen in Table 1 of the Problem Difficulty Criteria (Jakni, 2016):

Table 1 Question Difficulty Criteria

Tribulation Level Value	Information
0,00 – 0,30	Difficult
0,31 – 0,70	Keep
0,71 – 1,00	Easy

Differentiating power is an ability to distinguish between groups with high abilities and groups that have low abilities through learning outcomes tests (Amalia & Widayati, 2012). The differentiating power is determined by the following formula:

$$DP = \frac{B_A}{J_A} - \frac{B_B}{J_B}$$

The classification of differentiating power indices can be seen in Table 2 of the Distinguishing Power Index (Jakni, 2016):

Table 2 Differentiating Power Index

Distinguishing Power Value	Information
0,40 or more	Excellent
0,30 – 0,39	Good enough
0,20 – 0,29	Minimum
0,19 and below	Ugly

A distractor is an answer choice in multiple-choice tests that is close to the answer, so some of the many test takers who take the learning outcomes test are interested in choosing it (Amalia & Widayati, 2012). A deceiver or extractor can be said to be successful if it has a great appeal to the test taker (Purwanti, 2014). After that the data is processed to prove the correctness of the hypothesis that has been made. Data analysis techniques used in quantitative research use statistics. In carrying out data analysis, there are prerequisite tests for analysis and hypothesis tests.

The analysis prerequisite test uses a normality test as well as a homogeneity test. The normality test is used to find out whether the sample we have taken before is from a normal distributor or not. Homogeneity test to determine the differences of 2 groups of samples whether they have the same or different variants (Hestavia et al., 2019).

The normality test was carried out using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method, the research data can be said to be normally distributed if the sig value > 0.05. The homogeneity test was carried out using the Levene Statistic method, a significant level for the homogeneity test was 0.05. The balance test was used to determine whether the two groups studied had the same initial ability or were balanced. The balance test is calculated using a t test with $\alpha = 0.05$.

The hypothesis test was carried out using an independent sample t test to find out whether there is an influence on the use of an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository on student interests and learning outcomes by knowing the differences in student learning outcomes and interests. The formula used to measure the influence in the use of inquiry-based learning models assisted by open video repositories on student interests and learning outcomes:

$$\text{Normalized Gain (g)} = \frac{\text{posttest score} - \text{pretest score}}{\text{maximum score} - \text{pretest score}}$$

The following categories using the Normalized Gain index (g) according to (Hake, 1999) are found in the table:

Table 3 Normalized Gain Index (g)

Normalized Gain (G)	Criterion
$-1,00 < g < 0,00$	Very low
$g = 0,00$	Low
$0,00 < g < 0,30$	Enough
$0,30 < g < 0,70$	Good
$0,70 < g < 1,00$	Tall

The procedures or steps to be implemented in this study can be categorized into three stages, namely the research preparation stage, the research implementation stage, and the research completion stage. In the research preparation stage, the things that need to be done are to identify problems; design research or prepare proposals; as well as make research instruments and validate instruments. While at the stage of conducting the research, the steps that must be carried out are trial / try out of the instrument; analyzing the results of the trial / try out of the instrument; then determining the control class and experiment; then the final test (posttest) for the experimental class and the control

class. Meanwhile, at the stage of completing the research, the things that need to be done are to process the data from the research results; research discussion; drawing of research conclusions; and completion of research reports.

Result and Analysis

This research was used to find out how the influence and how much the increase in the use of the Inquiry Based Learning learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository was compared to the learning model that had been used previously, namely Discovery Learning. There are data obtained in this study including data on the learning outcomes of class X TJKT 1 and X TJKT 2 students with the subject matter of basic orientation of computer network and telecommunications engineering as well as data on the assessment of interest in learning the basics of computer network engineering and telecommunications.

Instrument Analysis

The instruments used in this study were questionnaire instruments and learning outcomes instruments. The instruments that will be given to the experimental class and the previous control class must have gone through the trial stage with a try out. The trial of this instrument was given to students of class XI TJKT 1 SMK 1 Sawit Boyolali, where this class is not a class in research and previously had also received material on the basic orientation of computer network engineering and telecommunications. The students who tried out were 35 students. Testing of this questionnaire instrument is carried out by testing its validity and reliability. Of the 35 learners who took part in the try out, it was known that $r_{table} = 0.334$. The results of the validity and reliability test of the questionnaire instrument from 30 questions, there were 23 questions that were declared valid. With a reliability value of 0.843.

Testing of learning outcome instruments that need to be carried out includes testing validity, reliability, difficulty levels, differences, and questioning. Based on the results of the test try out question instrument, there were 15 pretest questions that were declared valid and 16 posttest questions that were declared valid. The reliability trial yielded results of 0.893 for pretest questions and 0.857 for posttest questions, indicating a high level of reliability in both cases.

Data Description

Data on the results of the pretest and posttest that have been given to 36 students in the experimental class and 36 students in the control class as well as data from the results of the student learning interest questionnaire were processed using the help of the SPSS version 22 application.

Description of Student Learning Interest Pretest Data

Pretest data on student interest in learning is questionnaire data given to students before being given treatment in the form of Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model assisted by Open Video Repository.

Table 4 Description of Learning Interest Pretest Data

Learning Interest Statistics	Experimental Class	Control Class
Average	67,47	69,25
Lowest Value	45	44
Top Rated	80	78
Standard Deviation	8,355	6,398
Variance	69,799	40,936

The experimental class, comprising 36 students, had an average score of 67.47. Scores ranged from 45 to 80, with a standard deviation of 8.355 and a variance of 69,799. Meanwhile, the control class, consisting of 36 students, had an average score of 69.25. The scores ranged from a low of 44 to a high of 78, with a standard deviation of 6.398 and a variance of 40.936. The frequency distribution of pretest data on student learning interest in the experimental class amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 6. In intervals 45-50 it has a frequency of 2, intervals 51-56 have a frequency of 1, intervals 57-62 have a frequency of 8, intervals 63-68 have a frequency of 7, intervals 69-74 have a frequency of 11, and intervals 75-80 have a frequency of 7.

The frequency distribution of the control class pretest data pretested to 6 classes with an interval length of 6. In intervals 43-48 it has a frequency of 1, intervals 55-60 have a frequency of 1, intervals 61-66 have a frequency of 7, intervals 67-72 have a frequency of 17, and intervals 73-78 have a frequency of 10.

Description of Student Learning Interest Posttest Data

Posttest data for student learning interests is questionnaire data given to students after being given treatment in the form of an Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository.

Table 5 Description of Posttest Data On Learning Interest

Learning Interest Statistics	Experimental Class	Control Class
Average	75,69	72,89
Lowest Value	65	60
Top Rated	88	84
Standard Deviation	6,224	5,518
Variance	38,733	30,444

The experimental class, consisting of 36 students, achieved an average score of 75.69, with scores ranging from 65 to 88. The standard deviation was 6.224, and the variance was 38,733. Meanwhile, the control class, also comprising 36 students, attained an average score of 72.89. Scores ranged from 60 to 84, with a standard deviation of 5.518 and a variance of 30,444. The frequency distribution of the experimental class's posttest data was 6 classes with an interval length of 4. In intervals 65-68 it has a frequency of 5, intervals 69-72 have a frequency of 7, intervals 73-76 have a frequency of 9, intervals 77-80 have a frequency of 6, intervals 81-84 have a frequency of 6, and intervals 85-88 have a frequency of 3.

The frequency distribution of the control class learning interest posttest data amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 5. In intervals 58-62 it has a frequency of 2, intervals 63-67 have a frequency of 2, intervals 68-72 have a frequency of 14, intervals 73-77 have a frequency of 12, intervals 78-82 have a frequency of 5, and intervals 83-87 have a frequency of 1.

Description of Student Learning Outcomes Pretest Data

Pretest data on student learning outcomes represent the initial abilities of students before undergoing treatment, which involves the utilization of an Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) model supported by the Open Video Repository.

Table 6 Description of Pretest Learning Outcomes Data

Learning Interest Statistics	Experimental Class	Control Class
Average	54,33	54,42
Lowest Value	32	32
Top Rated	77	74
Standard Deviation	12,252	11,879
Variance	150,114	141,107

The experimental class, comprising 36 students, achieved an average score of 54.33. The scores ranged from 32 to 77, with a standard deviation of 12.252 and a variance of 150,114. Meanwhile, the control class, comprising 36 students, had an average score of 54.42. The scores ranged from a low of 32 to a high of 74, with a standard deviation of 11.879 and a variance of 141.107. The frequency distribution of pretest data on student learning outcomes scores in the experimental class amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 8. In intervals 30-37 it has a frequency of 5, intervals 38-45 have a frequency of 5, intervals 46-53 have a frequency of 4, intervals 54-61 have a frequency of 14, intervals 62-69 have a frequency of 5, and intervals 70-77 have a frequency of 3.

The frequency distribution of pretest data on the learning outcomes of the control class amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 8. In intervals 30-37 it has a frequency of 3, intervals 38-45 have a frequency of 6, intervals 46-53 have a frequency of 10, intervals 54-61 have a frequency of 6, intervals 62-69 have a frequency of 8, and intervals 70-77 have a frequency of 3.

Description of Student Learning Outcomes Posttest Data

Posttest data on student learning outcomes is data based on students' final abilities after being given treatment in the form of using an Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository.

Table 7 Description of Posttest Learning Outcomes Data

Learning Interest Statistics	Experimental Class	Control Class
Average	85,44	75,31
Lowest Value	74	55
Top Rated	97	87
Standard Deviation	6,254	7,091
Variance	39,111	50,275

The experimental class, consisting of 36 students, obtained an average score of 85.44, with scores ranging from 74 to 97. The standard deviation was 6,254, and the variance was 39,111. Meanwhile, the control class, consisting of 36 students, had an average score of 75.31. The scores ranged from a minimum of 55 to a maximum of 87, with a standard deviation of 7.091 and a variance of 50.275. The frequency distribution of data on posttest results of student learning outcomes in the experimental class amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 4. In intervals 74-77 it has a frequency of 6, the interval 78-81 has a frequency of 7, the interval 82-85 has a frequency of 4, the interval 86-89 has a frequency of 8, the interval 90-93 has a frequency of 4, and the interval 94-97 has a frequency of 7.

The frequency distribution of posttest data on the learning outcomes of the control class amounted to 6 classes with an interval length of 6. In intervals 52-57 it has a frequency of 1, the interval 58-63 has a frequency of 1, the interval 64-69 has a frequency of 4, the interval 70-75 has a frequency of 12, the interval 76-81 has a frequency of 11, and the interval 82-87 has a frequency of 7.

Prerequisite Test Result

Normality Test

The results of the normality test of pretest and posttest data of student learning interest for experimental and control classes can be seen in table 8.

Table 8 Learning Interest Normality Test

Category	Data	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Experimental Class	Pretest	0,188	0,05	Usual
	Posttest	0,200	0,05	Usual
Control Class	Pretest	0,190	0,05	Usual
	Posttest	0,200	0,05	Usual

In the experimental class, the significant calculation value of pretest data was 0.188 and posttest data was 0.200. While in the control class, it shows a significant calculated value of pretest data, which is 0.190 and posttest data is 0.200. The calculated value is significant > a significant level (0.05) then the pretest and posttest data of learning interest for the experimental class and the control class are normally distributed. The results of the normality test of pretest and posttest data learning outcomes for experimental classes and control classes can be seen in table 9.

Table 9 Normality Test: Learning Outcomes

Category	Data	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Experimental Class	Pretest	0,109	0,05	Usual
	Posttest	0,160	0,05	Usual
Control Class	Pretest	0,200	0,05	Usual
	Posttest	0,146	0,05	Usual

The experimental class showed a significant count value of the pretest was 0.109 and the posttest was 0.160. Meanwhile, the control class showed a significant calculation value of pretest data, which was 0.200 and posttest data was 0.146. The calculated value is significant > a significant level (0.05) then the pretest and posttest data of learning outcomes for the experimental class and the control class are normally distributed.

Homogeneity Test

The results of the homogeneity test of posttest data on learning interests for experimental classes and control classes can be seen in table 10.

Table 10 Learning Interest Homogeneity Test

Category	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Pretest	0,084	0,05	Homogeneous
Posttest	0,490	0,05	Homogeneous

The significant calculated value of the learning interest homogeneity test based on the pretest value is $0.084 > 0.05$ while the posttest value is $0.490 > 0.05$, so that both classes are categorized as homogeneous. The results of the homogeneity test of posttest data learning outcomes for experimental and control classes can be seen in table 11.

Table 11 Learning Outcome Homogeneity Test

Category	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Pretest	0,966	0,05	Homogeneous
Posttest	0,815	0,05	Homogeneous

The significant calculated value of the homogeneity test of learning outcomes based on the pretest value is $0.966 > 0.05$ while the posttest value is $0.815 > 0.05$, so that both classes are categorized as homogeneous.

Balance Test

The balance test is calculated using a t test with $\alpha = 0.05$. Learning interest pretest data balance test results for experimental classes and control classes.

Table 12 Study Interest Balance Test

Category	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Pretest	0,314	0,05	Balanced

The significant calculated value of the learning interest balance test based on the pretest value is $0.314 > 0.05$, so that both classes are categorized as balanced. Results of the pretest data balance test of learning outcomes for experimental classes and control classes.

Table 13 Learning Outcomes Balance Test

Category	Sig	Significant Level	Information
Pretest	0,977	0,05	Balanced

The significant calculation value of the learning outcomes balance test based on the pretest value is $0.977 > 0.05$, so that the two classes are categorized as balanced.

Hypothesis Test Results

First Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no difference in students' learning interests using the Inquiry Based Learning (IBL) learning model assisted by the Open Video Repository.

H_a : There are variations in student learning interests when using the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) model supported by the Open Video Repository.

Table 14 Independent Sample T Test Results Study Interest

Variance Equation	Levene's Test		T Test	
	F	Sig.	t	Sig. (2- tailed)
Assumed	0,482	0,490	2,024	0,047

Not Assumed	2,024	0,047
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The results of the independent sample t test obtained an F value of 0.482 and a significance value of 0.490 greater than the significance level (0.05) so that the two classes did not have variance. On the sig value. (2- tailed) contained in the row is assumed to be 0.047 where the sig value is. (2- tailed) is less than the significance level, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Therefore, there is an influence on the use of an inquiry-based learning (IBL) learning model assisted by an open video repository on the interest in learning in the basics of TJKT subjects for students of SMK N 1 Sawit. The inquiry learning model in its learning resulted in an increase in student interest in learning after using the inquiry learning model (Purwiningsih & Sari, 2022). Inquiry learning models can be used to reduce student barriers to learning, through inquiry learning students have the opportunity to solve problems individually or in groups, train students to interact and exchange information with friends, and improve cognitive abilities (Maulidiyah & Hasanah, 2019).

Second Hypothesis

H₀ : Employing the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) model with assistance from the Open Video Repository does not yield any discernible discrepancy in student learning outcomes..

H_a : Implementing the Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) model with assistance from the Open Video Repository leads to variations in student learning outcomes.

Table 15 Independent Sample T Test Results Learning Outcomes

Variance Equation	Levene's Test		T Test	
	F	Sig.	t	Sig. (2- tailed)
Assumed	0,055	0,815	6,434	0,000
Not Assumed			6,434	0,000

The results of the independent sample t test obtained an F value of 0.055 and a significance value of 0.815 greater than the significance level (0.05) so that the two classes did not have variance. On the sig value. (2- tailed) contained in the row is assumed to be 0.000 where the sig value is. (2- tailed) is less than the significance level, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. Therefore, there is an influence in the use of an inquiry-based learning (IBL) learning model assisted by an open video repository on learning outcomes in the basics of TJKT subjects for students of SMK N 1 Sawit. The application of the guided inquiry learning model, there is an average increase in student learning outcomes using the guided inquiry learning model (Aryanto & Shofiyullah, 2022). Cognitive learning activities and outcomes of students who have improved after applying the Inquiry Based Learning learning model (Lukas Liku Kadiwone et al., 2022).

Third Hypothesis

To find out the increased interest in learning students of experimental and control classes can use the Gain Test.

Table 16 Learning Interest Gain Test Results

Class	Average		Gain Score	Information
	Pretest	Posttest		
Experiment	67,47	75,69	0,32	Good
Control	69,25	72,89	0,16	Enough

The gain value in the experimental class is 0.32 with the good category, and in the control class it is 0.16 with the sufficient category. When compared to the total gain score, the use of an inquiry-based learning (IBL) learning model assisted by an open video repository is more effective than the previous learning model.

Fourth Hypothesis

To find out the improvement of learning outcomes of students in the experimental and control classes, you can use the Gain Test.

Table 17 Learning Outcome Gain Test Results

Class	Average		Gain Score	Information
	Pretest	Posttest		

Experiment	54,33	85,44	0,68	Good
Control	54,42	75,31	0,44	Good

The gain value in the experimental class is 0.68 with the good category, and in the control class it is 0.44 with the good category. When compared to the total gain score, the use of an inquiry-based learning (IBL) learning model assisted by an open video repository is more effective than the previous learning model.

In this study, the existence of an open video repository can help the learning process in providing understanding to students. The open video repository can be used as a learning resource for students because it can be accessed anywhere and anytime through the website. During the learning process, the use of open video repositories is applied at the conceptualization stage in the inquiry-based learning model. In this stage, students are given an understanding of the concept of the problem to produce a hypothesis that can then be researched. The conceptualization syntax is carried out by the way the teacher provides learning topics, guides and facilitates students to find, understand, and formulate problems with the help of an open video repository.

Inquiry-based learning models include discovery, but have a higher level. The discovery learning model is to assimilate a concept or principle by observing various things that exist in the environment, and children assimilate it through the concept of livestock, the principle of heat, the principle of falling, etc. Meanwhile, in the inquiry-based learning model, there are psychological processes such as asking questions, designing experiments, conducting experiments, collecting data, analyzing and drawing conclusions (Fathurrohman, 2015).

During the use of this inquiry-based learning model, the curriculum used is an independent curriculum, where students are given freedom in finding learning resources and most of the students use the internet as a source of information. Therefore, using the open video repository platform which contains learning materials and videos can make it easier for students to understand the learning material.

Conclusion

This study is to find out whether there are differences in influence and improvement in the use of inquiry-based learning models, including open video repository, on the interests and learning outcomes of students.

There are differences in the learning interests of students who use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository with classes that do not use it. When the learning process takes place, students have a high interest in classroom learning that uses an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository. Student interest during the learning process increases. Many students began to actively ask about learning the Basics of Computer Network engineering and Telecommunications. So it can be said that the inquiry-based learning model assisted by open video repositories has a significant influence on students' learning interests.

There are differences in student learning outcomes between students who use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository and classes that do not use it. Based on the results of the study, the learning outcomes of students who used an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository have increased. So it can be said that the inquiry-based learning model assisted by the open video repository has a significant influence on student learning outcomes.

The use of an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository has a higher effectiveness compared to those who do not use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository based on students' learning interests. The learning that occurs between the experimental class and the control class has differences. In classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository, the interest in learning is higher than in classes that do not use the learning model. This can be proven by the results of the gain test where classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository have higher results than classes that do not use it.

The use of an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository has a higher effectiveness compared to those who do not use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository based on student learning outcomes. The learning that occurs between the experimental class and the control class has differences. In classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository, the interest in learning is higher than in classes that do not use the learning model. This can be proven by the results of the gain test where classes that use an inquiry-based learning model assisted by an open video repository have higher results than classes that do not use it.

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